

Structural Study of Metal Chelates derived from Tridentate Ligand

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Oxovanadium(IV), chromium(III), manganese(II), iron(II), cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes of the Schiff base derived from salicylhydrazide and 6-methyl-4-hydroxy-3-acetylcoumarin (Me-HACSH) have been synthesised having 1:1 metal-ligand ratio. The complexes are of non-electrolytic nature except that of the oxovanadium(IV) complex which is found to be a 1:1 electrolyte. The ligand acts as dibasic tridentate and forms oxygen-bridged polymeric structures for all complexes except the oxovanadium(IV) where it acts as a monobasic tridentate ligand forming dimeric structure. Distorted octahedral geometry has been proposed for the complexes.

We have reported earlier the transition metal complexes of benzoxazoles and coumarins^{1,2}. A similar study of oxovanadium(IV), Cr^{III}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of the Schiff base derived from salicylhydrazide and 6-methyl-4-hydroxy-3-acetylcoumarin (Me-HACSH) is reported here.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes (Table 1) are coloured, stable to air and moisture, and decompose at high temperature. They are sparingly soluble in DMF, DMSO and dioxane but insoluble in common organic solvents. Conductance values indicate their non-electrolytic nature, except oxovanadium(IV) which is 1:1 electrolyte.

Salicylhydrazone exhibits metal binding in two tautomeric forms, ketoform and enol (Fig. 1). The enolic form can be identified by the absence of their peak at 1625 cm⁻¹ (C=O) and the presence of a new peak at 1270–1280 cm⁻¹ (C–O). The keto form is preferred by the oxovanadium(IV) complex while the enol form by the Cr^{II}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes.

IR spectra of the complexes show characteristic features indicative of the changes undergone by the ligand Me-HACSH, during the complexation. The free ligand shows IR bands at 3260, 3200–2900, 1700, 1625, 1600, 1530, 1490 cm⁻¹ assignable to ν_{NH} , ν_{OH} (hydrogen bonded), $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ (lactone), $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ of salicyl moi-

ety, $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$, $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ (phenolic) of salicyl moiety and $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ (phenolic) of coumarin moiety respectively. In solid state the ligand stabilises only the keto form. In the case of the oxovanadium(IV) and copper(II) complexes, a strong peak is observed at 3500–3530 cm⁻¹ characteristic of ν_{OH} , indicating cleavage of hydrogen bonding and non-participation of oxygen of phenolic group of coumarin moiety in coordination. In all the complexes except oxovanadium(IV), the presence of a broad band at 3500–3400 cm⁻¹ suggests the overlapping of coordinated water and phenolic-OH of the coumarin moiety. The presence of coordinated water in these complexes except oxovanadium(IV) is confirmed by DT and TG analysis and non-ligand bands around 820–830 cm⁻¹ (Ref. 3). In all complexes, a positive shift to the extent of 15–20 cm⁻¹ is observed in $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ indicating the deprotonation of salicyl phenolic group and subsequently bridging of the oxygen to the metal ions. This large positive shift indicates that oxygen is acting as bridging centre^{4,5}. The interesting observation was the negative shift to the extent of 10–30 cm⁻¹ in $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ (lactone) in all the complexes except in the Cr^{III} and Cu^{II} complexes, suggesting the participation of lactone carbonyl in complexation to give dimeric polymeric species^{6,7}. In all the complexes except oxovanadium(IV) complex, absence of bands due to ν_{NH} and $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ (salicyl moiety) suggests the enolisation of salicyl keto

group during complexation. The enolisation is further confirmed by a new non-ligand band around 1 280–1 270 cm^{-1} . In the oxovanadium(IV) complex the band

rest of the complexes it acts as dibasic tridentate with OON donor sequence. Oxygen of lactone carbonyl is participating in case of the oxovanadium(IV), Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} .

TABLE I – ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES*

Compd / Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Caled.)				
	Metal	C	H	N	Cl
[Oxovanadium(IV) (Me-HACSH)] ₂ SO ₄	9.95	44.50	2.95	5.50	
[(VC ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₆ N ₂) ₂]SO ₄	(9.91)	44.37	2.919	5.44)	
[Cr(III) Me-HACSHCl.H ₂ O] _n	11.50	49.98	3.75	6.20	7.67
(CrC ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₆ N ₂ Cl) _n	(11.39)	49.95	3.72	6.13	7.77)
[Mn(II) Me-HACHS.H ₂ O] _n	12.90	53.90	4.10	6.65	-
(MnC ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₆ N ₂) _n	(12.95)	53.78	4.01	6.60)	
[Fe(II) Me-HACSH.H ₂ O] _n	12.65	51.50	4.50	6.50	-
(FeC ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₇ N ₂) _n	(12.61)	51.49	4.29	6.32)	
[Co(II) Me-HACSH.H ₂ O] _n	13.20	51.20	4.28	6.30	-
(CoC ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₇ N ₂) _n	(13.21)	51.13	4.26	6.27)	
[Ni(II) Me-HACSH.H ₂ O] _n	13.80	53.50	3.95	6.60	-
(NiC ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₆ N ₂) _n	(13.72)	53.31	3.97	6.54)	
[Cu(II) Me-HACSH.2H ₂ O] _n	14.20	50.70	4.25	6.28	-
(CuC ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₇ N ₂) _n	(14.10)	50.61	4.21	6.21)	

*Satisfactory results have been obtained for sulphur analysis.

due to ν_{NH} is persistent and $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ (salicyl moiety) appears at 1 630 cm^{-1} indicating rupture of hydrogen bonding and subsequent participation of oxygen of carbonyl group of the salicyl moiety in coordination. A positive shift by 10 cm^{-1} is observed in the spectrum of oxovanadium(IV) complex which is attributed to the participation of nitrogen of the azomethine group in coordination⁸. The appearance of doublet at 1 605–1 620 cm^{-1} in the complexes except the oxovanadium(IV), suggests the enolisation of the ligand giving rise to another C=N group. In the doublet, one of the peak is due to new C=N and the other one can be attributed to the original C=N which has undergone positive shift suggesting the participation of the nitrogen of this azomethine group on coordination. A broad band at 1 020–920 cm^{-1} is observed in the case of the oxovanadium(IV) complex which may be due to ionic sulphate and $\nu_{\text{V-O}}$ vibration^{9,10}. The new bands of medium intensity in the region 600–400 cm^{-1} are assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ vibrations and the 285 cm^{-1} band is assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-Cl}}$ mode^{11,12}. On the basis of ir spectral studies it is concluded that in case of the oxovanadium(IV) complex the ligand acts as monobasic tridentate with ONO donor sequence. But in the

Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes but it is not so in the case of the Cr^{III} and Cu^{II} complexes.

The magnetic moment values of all the complexes have been observed to be lower than the respective spin-only values. In a large number of tridentate ONO donor metal complexes, lower magnetic moment have been reported^{4,13} which have been attributed to antiferromagnetic interactions as a consequence of dimeric or polymeric structural arrangements. The oxovanadium(IV) complex is paramagnetic. The room temperature magnetic moment is 1.65 B.M., which may be due to metal-metal interaction. The electronic spectrum of the oxovanadium(IV) complex shows two bands at 13 090–13 340 and 16 800–16 950 cm^{-1} assigned to ${}^2b_2 \rightarrow {}^2e$, ${}^2b_2 \rightarrow {}^2b_1$ transitions respectively, which are consistent with distorted octahedral geometry¹⁴. The observed magnetic moment of the Cr^{III} complex at room temperature is 3.2 B.M. The Cr^{III} complex shows three main bands at 12 000, 18 180 and 25 000 cm^{-1} which are assignable to ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$, ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g} (I')$ and ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} (P)$ transitions respectively. These transitions are consistent with distorted octahedral geometry^{15,16}. The Mn^{II} complex possesses room temperature magnetic moment value of 4.65 B.M. which

is low compared to spin-only value for high-spin manganese(II) complexes. The weak electronic spectral bands of the Mn^{II} complex are not of much help in deciding the geometry. The room temperature magnetic

Fig. 1. Tautomeric form of Me-HACSH

moment of the Fe^{II} complex is 4.9 B.M. The electronic spectrum of the Fe^{II} complex displays a band at $12\,120\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is ascribed to ${}^5T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^5E_g$ transition¹⁷. The slightly low value of magnetic moment of the Co^{II} complex (4.3 B.M.) is due to metal-metal interactions. The Co^{II} complex exhibits two distinct bands at $18\,180$ and $25\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which can be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} (P)$, ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g} (F)$ respectively. These bands suggest distorted octahedral geometry for the complex¹⁷. The observed magnetic moment of the Ni^{II} complex is 2.65 B.M. which is expected for six-coordinated nickel(II) complexes. The electronic spectrum of the Ni^{II} complex shows three bands at $10\,810$, $16\,666$ and $25\,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which are assigned to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g} (I')$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g} (P)$ transitions respectively, which are in the range required for distorted octahedral geometry¹⁷. The Cu^{II} complex possesses magnetic moment of 1.6 B.M. The low value may be due to metal-metal interaction. The Cu^{II} complex exhibits one broad band at $14\,050\text{--}15\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is assignable to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition of dis-

torted octahedral geometry¹⁷. The broadness of the band is due to the Jahn-Teller distortions.

The esr spectra of the oxovanadium(IV) and Cu^{II} complexes do not show any resolution at $g_{\perp}$ region so it can be assumed that g_x and g_y are same or nearly the same. The g values of 1.972^{15,18} and 2.214¹⁹ for oxovanadium(IV) and Cu^{II} complexes respectively. These g values indicate strong interaction between the ligand and the metal ion and hence distorted octahedral geometry is proposed.

TG analysis shows that loss of water occurs in a two-step process as evidenced by endothermic peaks at 190 and 240° for the Cu^{II} complex. For other complexes, the loss of water occurs in one step process at 180 , 200 , 210 and 220° for the Cr^{III} , Mn^{II} , Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes respectively.

On the basis of the above studies it is concluded that the ligand acts as monobasic tridentate with ONO sequence, forming oxygen-bridged dimeric structure in the case of the oxovanadium(IV) complex, but in the rest of the complexes it acts as dibasic tridentate with OON sequence forming oxygen-bridged polymeric structures. On the basis of magnetic and electronic spectral data, distorted octahedral geometry for all the complexes is proposed.

Experimental

All the metal halides and sulphates used were of A.R. grade. 6-Methyl-4-hydroxy-3-acetylcoumarin was prepared according to the reported method²⁰. The Schiff base was prepared by refluxing a mixture of salicylhydrazide and 6-methyl-4-hydroxy-3-acetylcoumarin in 1:1 molar ratio in methanol for 2 h. The product was crystallised from EtOH-DMF mixture, (m.p $199\text{--}200^{\circ}$). The purity of the ligand was ascertained by tlc.

The metal chelates were prepared by refluxing the respective metal chlorides (0.01 mol) and the ligand (0.01 mol) in methanol (100 ml) for 2-3 h. In the case of the oxovanadium(IV) and Fe^{II} complexes, the metal salts used were vanadyl sulphate and ferrous-ammonium sulphate. The pH of the solution was adjusted to ~ 7 by 1:1 NH_3 in methanol in case of the Ni^{II} complex. The metal chelates were washed with MeOH followed by petroleum ether (b.p. $60\text{--}80^{\circ}$) and dried under reduced pressure (yields 50-60%).

Electrical conductance was measured on Digisun Electronics D₁-909 and Systronics 304 instruments. The complexes were analysed for their metal contents employing standard procedures after destroying the organic matter with nitric acid, chloride was estimated as AgCl and sulphate as BaSO₄. Nitrogen was determined by microanalysis. The magnetic susceptibility was determined by Guoy method using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as the calibrant, and the values were corrected for diamagnetism²¹ and temperature-independent magnetic moment. The electronic spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Carry-14 spectrophotometer, infrared spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and esr spectra on a JEOL-JES-F3X spectrometer as powder at room temperature. TG analysis was carried out on a manually operated thermobalance with a heating rate of 5° per min. Differential thermal analysis was carried out using Leeds and Northrup DTA units (U.S.A.) with a heating rate of 10° per min.

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